

Deliverable 7.3

Project identity and website

Work package number and title:	WP7: Communication, dissemination and future engagement
Lead-beneficiary:	EUFIC
Work package Leader:	EUFIC
Relevant Task:	7.3 Development of project identity, templates and website
Dissemination Level:	Public
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1. Introduction

Deliverable D7.3 describes the process and outcome of Task 7.3, which includes the development of the FIT4FOOD2030 project identity and website. The project identity includes a logo and communication templates, which ensures a common graphic/visual line to be easily recognised among external stakeholders.

The process started by setting up a “**FIT4FOOD2030 Communications Working Group**” (**MS1, achieved on 2 November 2017**), comprising a subgroup of partners from the consortium: VU, ILSI Europe, JPI HDHL, and EUFIC. The aim of this working group is to have an efficient process of deciding on the project’s visual identity, as well as communications strategy and messages. Involving a smaller group of partners, who are keen to provide feedback on communication related matters, is more efficient than asking the entire consortium for their input on a project logo, which also has a subjective side to it. Still, making sure different partners are heard, guarantees that different views are incorporated.

After several conversations with the European Commission (EC) it was decided that the visual identity of FIT4FOOD2030 would closely match that of the existing FOOD 2030 branding, to give the project the recognition and endorsement from the EC it needs to efficiently support the rolling out of the FOOD 2030 policy framework.

The public facing website is a portal for information about the project targeted to all potential stakeholders. It will be updated continuously throughout the project lifetime with input from all partners and will be maintained for a certain period beyond the project as well.

2. FIT4FOOD2030 project identity & logo

Initially, the graphic design agency was briefed to design logo proposals that would *match* the existing FOOD 2030 logo (figure 1), including the following concepts to be reflected:

- The project **supports the implementation** of the FOOD 2030 policy framework (which already has its logo, colours, and visuals).
- **Responsible** Research & Innovation (this is about the emphasis on **engaging with stakeholders** as a basis for the investment in research)
- The main outcome of the project: **a sustainable multi-stakeholder, multi-level (1. cities/regions, 2. countries, and 3. Europe) platform**
- The four priority areas of FOOD 2030: **nutrition, climate, circularity, innovation.**

Figure 1 – FOOD 2030 logo

This resulted in the logo proposals shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 – initial logo proposals.

At that moment, the EC realised they wanted FIT4FOOD2030's branding matching more closely to the existing FOOD 2030 branding, which resulted in another set of proposals, shown in figure 3. Finally, on 18 December 2017, the Communication Working Group and the EC decided for the logo at the bottom-left in figure 3, which can also be seen in the header of this document.

Figure 3 – second round of logo proposals.

The graphic charter, including the rules regarding the graphic identity of the project, was finalised on 9 January (figure 4).

Figure 4 – FIT4FOOD2030 Graphic Charter

3. Templates

The graphic charter and logo were the point of reference for designing the communication templates and bookmark, which functions as the project’s leaflet and can be printed as a roll-up. The development process consisted of several rounds of iteration and input from the Communication Working Group has been integrated.

The templates – Word and PowerPoint (presentation and poster) – aim to achieve a consistent project identity within the consortium as well as awareness and recognition among external stakeholders. The project logo, EU emblem and funding disclaimer (contract number), and project website (www.fit4food2030.eu) and hashtag (#FOOD2030EU) are displayed on all templates.

The templates form the basis for all project communication and dissemination materials and can be shaped into different materials, based on the needs of the project partners.

The templates (see figure 5) have been made available to all project partners via Edugroepen (extranet) on 16 April 2018. All project partners are encouraged to use the templates in all communication about the project.

Figure 5 – FIT4FOOD2030 templates: Word landscape/portrait (top), PowerPoint slides (middle), and poster (bottom)

The bookmark – project leaflet and roll-up for events – is the first, general dissemination material, which can be used to hand out to stakeholders. It supports the first phase of the project’s communication in which building the ‘FIT4FOOD2030 brand’ and increasing its visibility is key.

Figure 6 – FIT4FOOD2030 bookmark (front and back side)

The project bookmark, also made available to all project partners via Edugroepen (extranet) on 16 April 2018, will be printed and sent to all project partners.

4. External website

The FIT4FOOD2030 website is the main hub for information about the project targeted to all potential stakeholders. It will be updated continuously throughout the project lifetime with input from all partners and will be maintained for a certain period beyond the project as well.

As shortly after the project’s kick-off some partners needed a place for project information online, it was decided to develop a temporary website, simultaneously to the development of the project identity and templates. The temporary website (www.fit4food2030.eu) went live on 12 December 2017 (figure 7).

Figure 7 – Screenshots of the FIT4FOOD2030 temporary website (www.fit4food2030.eu), went live on 12 December 2017.

For the permanent website, incorporating the FIT4FOOD2030 graphic identity, it was explored how the project’s main output – the FOOD 2030 Platform – could be visualised and integrated. The idea arose – although adding a bit more complexity than initially foreseen – to develop an interactive map of Europe in which activating filters would allow users to show the City Labs, Policy Labs and EU Thinktank, respectively.

The project website includes the following sections:

- About (including *aims and objectives, expected outcomes, and concepts & methods*)
- FOOD 2030
- Project activities (*including the interactive map of Europe – see above*)
- FOOD 2030 Platform
- Project partners
- News
- Publications
- Contact details

Other elements of the website are social media buttons, newsletter sign-up, and some interactive features to show different website content. The website went live on 28 April 2018 (figure 8).

The website, coordinated and maintained by EUFIC, will be hosted for the duration of the project, plus three years after completion of the project.

Figure 8 – Screenshots of the FIT4FOOD2030 website (www.fit4food2030.eu), went live on 28 April 2017.